

Development of simplified models for the individuation of the proper exploitation method for African Geothermal resources

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Abstract:

Low to high enthalpy geothermal resources exist across the African continent, however, the utilization is still minimal. East Africa has well-known high enthalpy geothermal resources due to its geological setting (East African Rift System). The potential for power generation related to this favourable geological condition is extensive, but geothermal development has (to date) been limited. The current focus is mainly on high-temperature resources (i.e., East African Rift), while low-medium systems are neglected, even though they could provide sustainable heat/energy sources for industrial purposes, tourism, and others. Within the Leap RE project and particularly to WP9, it is expected to implement a Geothermal Atlas for Africa by identifying collecting, compiling, and (re)processing existing data to create an up-to-date Atlas and to help identify the optimal exploitation sites.

A specific objective of the WP is to propose the optimal exploitation technologies (both from an economic and environmental point of view) as a function of the geothermal resource type. To do so, it is necessary to develop simplified geothermal models which could be inserted in a global optimization method to select the preferable option to leverage geothermal energy.

Therefore, in this work, the development of the simplified thermodynamic, economic and environmental models is described. The first obtained selection maps are drawn as preliminary results of the work.

Keywords:

Economic, Thermodynamic, geothermal, environmental, optimization

1. Introduction

Climate change and environmental pollution are becoming an increasingly serious problem, which is why the European Commission is proposing a new strategy to eliminate atmospheric CO₂ emissions by 2050, decouple economic growth from resources, and ensure that no person or place is neglected, through the Green Deal [1].

Also, the Department of Economic and Social Affairs of United Nation are working on the sustainable topic and the world's most critical problems. They have produced the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, which is a project structured around 17 Sustainable Development Goals. Each of these has a specific purpose and touches on a wide variety of sensitive issues such as poverty, world hunger, education, water availability and much more. The seventh point is dedicated to energy, and the goal is to make energy accessible, reliable, resilient, sustainable, and modern for all [2].

The European Union's framework program Horizon 2020 and its successor Horizon Europe for research and innovation, which aims to strengthen the scientific and technological foundations, implement European policies to meet the global challenges proposed by the SDGs, and strengthen European research, are part of this. In 2019, the President of the European Research Council met with both African and European research representatives to develop collaboration and cooperation between the two continents under the Horizon 2020 program [3]. This summit agreed with the African Union 2063 agenda, which is developed to define a common strategy for the continent for sustainable development focusing on the use of renewable energy [4].

In this panorama comes out the Long-term joint European union – African union research and innovation Partnership on Renewable Energy (LEAP – RE) which allows for collaboration between more than 80 African and European partners in government, research, private sector, and civil society. The aim of the project is to focus on the field of renewable energies and to support research and innovation for both Europe and Africa by

sharing knowledge, efficient methods of solving climate change problems, and providing access to energy for all (<https://www.leap-re.eu/>).

The work presented in this article concerns the engineering aspects of implementing the geothermal atlas for Africa. The aim of this work package is to define the location and condition of all exploitable geothermal resources for the purpose of electricity production or direct use of heat.

An intense and time-consuming study is needed in order to identify, collect and analyze all African data refer to: geological, geochemical and geophysical, technological (engineering) and all social aspects.

At the moment, the engineering partners are focusing on high-medium enthalpy resources for power generation. What is proposed is the realization of a model that, based on the conditions of the geothermal resource, predicts the performance of an optimized geothermal power plant considering also its the economic and environmental cost.

2. Methodology

Starting with a reference from various existing geothermal plant typologies, like dry steam, single-flash, double-flash and ORC, was possible to identify the main components and correlation of each plant. In particular the examined plants are: Chiusdino (dry steam), Hellisheiði (double-flash), Kizildere (triple-flash e ORC), Bagnore (double-flash e ORC) and Castelnuovo (ORC). On this analysis is based the generation of a generic model, useful to study any kind of geothermal plant and observe the most suitable for an available resource.

2.1. Block Modelling

In order to identify the most promising surface installation given the resource condition, the code analyse different power plant configuration and for each one calculates the expected LCOE and environmental cost. Plant configurations are defined as different combination of standardized components, listed in the table 1.

Table 1. Standardized Components.

Component	Parameters	Scheme
Flash Stage	<p><i>Input:</i> input brine conditions, relative quality in the separator (x_{rel}), condenser temperature</p> <p><i>Output:</i> power generated, Output brine condition, Output vapour condition, Stage Capital Cost</p>	
ORC Stage	<p><i>Input:</i> input brine conditions, RH dimension, condenser temperature, ORC fluid</p> <p><i>Output:</i> net power output, output brine condition, stage capital cost, condenser power and temperature (for DH purpose)</p>	
Well	<p><i>Input:</i> reservoir condition, well depth, brine flow rate</p> <p><i>Output:</i> well capital cost, output conditions, number of wells</p>	
Condenser	<p><i>Input:</i> input conditions, condenser temperature</p> <p><i>Output:</i> condenser capital cost</p>	
DH heat exchanger	<p><i>Input:</i> input conditions, outlet brine temperature</p> <p><i>Output:</i> heat exchanger capital cost, DH power</p>	

Figure 1. Software working principle

Figure 2. Configurations search tree example

Each component (also called block in the following) model has two kind of inputs:

- the **brine inlet conditions**, i.e. the reservoir condition or the outlet of a previous block,
- Some **design parameter**, such as the efficiency of the turbine or the selected ORC fluid, that are specific for each block and optimized by the overall code.

Moreover, each block must provide the brine outlet condition as a result in order to allow the code to connect another block in series if necessary. Due to their complexity, *flash stage* and *ORC* component's thermodynamic behaviour and capital investment has been modelled using some dedicated metamodelling in order to speed up computational time. For other components simple correlation has been considered. In order to generate the metamodelling, both ORC and Flash Stage blocks have been modelled in EES [10] and evaluated over a wide range of input condition and design parameters, the results have then been used in a dedicated RStudio code to generate the actual metamodel [9].

2.1.1. Overall Calculation As shown in Figure 1, the code combines those components to form a geothermal plant considering three main sections:

- **Production section**: models the raising of the fluid from the reservoir
- **Surface Plant section**: models the power extraction from the brine, it can be configured chaining multiple ORC or Flash stages in series and adding water condenser or a DH heat exchanger if needed.
- **Re-injection section**: models the re-injection of the fluid in the reservoir

The best configuration for the given design condition is identified by the code analysing all the possible configuration using a *configuration search tree* as the one depicted in Figure 2. Such tree is designed so that the software starts the analysis with the simplest configuration and then proceeds toward more complex schemes by adding stages to the power plant. The software will stop to go deeper in the analysis when it finds schemes in which the increased complexity does not leads to an increase in plant performance. For example, as shown in Figure 2, if the minimum LCOE predicted for the scheme C_i in a given condition is higher than the ones calculated for the scheme B_0 , the program will not analyse any schemes that is child of C_i . What follows is a detailed description of the thermodynamic, economic and environmental correlations used to model the two most important blocks, i.e. the *ORC* and *flash stage* blocks.

2.2. Thermodynamic Modelling

2.2.1. Flash Stage Block

A schematic of the Flash Stage Block is shown in Figure 3a. The incoming brine is laminated by a valve through an isenthalpic process, after the valve, the saturated liquid is separated from the vapor. The vapor side will proceed towards the turbine, while the liquid can be used as an input for another block or eventually discharged into the reinjection well. The steam entering the turbine will be expanded to produce useful work and then continue towards the condenser, not included in the block model as it can be shared by multiple stages, current metamodel consider the temperature of the condenser as fixed to 40°C, newer version will implement it as a variable parameter. Input condition and parameters are shown in Table 2 together with the ranges considered in the metamodel generation:

Table 2. Flash Stage parameters and input condition

Parameter	Range	Units
T_{in}	80-250	°C
$\dot{m}_{brine\ in}$	1 – 200	kg/s
x_{rel}	0-1	-
η_{turb}	0.75-0.95	-

Where:

- T_{in} is the brine inlet temperature (supposed in saturated liquid state). If the actual inlet brine is subcooled, the code will automatically consider an isentropic expansion to reach the saturation state. This will allow to avoid the need of considering P_{in} as a parameter, simplifying the metamodel generation process.
- x_{rel} is a parameter defined as follows:

$$x_{rel} = \frac{x_{sep}}{x_{sep,max}} \text{ with } x_{sep,max} = \text{quality}(h = h_{in}, P = P_{cond}) \quad (1)$$

Where P_{cond} is the pressure of the condenser and h_{in} is the inlet enthalpy. Such definition guarantees that, for each value of x_{rel} in the 0-1 range, the pressure inside the separator is higher than the one in the condenser, so that the turbine can extract power from the fluid. This make the calculation very

stable in the selected range and simplify the definition of the metamodel. Please note that this parameter is the key of the flash block modelling, it will be optimized in the overall code.

Figure 3. Flash stage (a) and ORC (b) blocks diagram

2.2.2. ORC Cycle Block

A schematic of the ORC Block can be seen in the Figure 3b. Evaporator pressure and ORC flow rates have been optimized for each point used for the metamodel generation, a separator has been inserted before the turbine, as shown in the scheme, in order to assure that only pure vapour is injected in the turbine and hence stabilize the convergence.

HRSG efficiency has been fixed to 0.8 and, in addition, brine temperature decrease has been limited to 90 °C in order to avoid extreme re-injection condition that could create thermal stress and induced seismicity in the reservoir. Condenser saturation temperature has been also fixed to 40°C.

Currently no regenerative heat exchanger has been considered in the metamodel but it will be implemented in the near future. Moreover, in the development of the newer version of the metamodel condenser saturation temperature is planned to be considered as a variable while HRSG and regenerator efficiencies will be selected minimizing the LCOE.

Different metamodels have been developed for each ORC fluid selection and brine input conditions. Implemented fluids are *R1233zd(E)*, *R1234yf*, and *n-pentane*, the first two have been selected for their low environmental impact, while the last one because it is a standard in the geothermal energy sector. Moreover, two different brine inlet condition has been selected, saturated liquid and saturated vapour, hence in total 6 different metamodels have been developed (2 for each fluid). The overall code automatically selects the right one to use based on the input condition. For each metamodel, the input parameters and ranges are very similar to the ones defined for the flash stage metamodel and are listed in the Table 3.

Table 3. ORC Cycle parameters and input condition

Parameter	Range	Units
T_{in}	80-250	°C
$\dot{m}_{brine\ in}$	1 – 200	kg/s
η_{turb}	0.75-0.95	-

2.3 Economy Modelling

To assess the cost of the components, there were used cost correlations shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Components cost correlations

Component	Quantities	Relation	Reference
Condenser	S = Surface of thermal exchange	$CP[0] = 10^{K_1+K_2 \cdot \log_{10} S + K_3 \cdot \log_{10} S^2}$	[11]
Heat Exchanger	[m ²]	$F_p = 10^{C_1+C_2 \cdot \log_{10} P + C_3 \cdot \log_{10} P^2}$	
HRSG	P = Operating pressure [bar]	$C_{BM} = CP[0] \cdot (B_1 + B_2 \cdot F_M \cdot F_P)$	
Recuperator			
Cooling Tower	Q _{COND} =condenser heat exchanged T _{CW} =temperature of inlet air	$C_{BM} = 70,5 \cdot Q_{COND} \cdot -0,6936 \cdot \ln(T_{CW} - T_{WB}) + 2,1898$	[13]

	T_{wb} = temperature of wet bulbe		
	W_p = Pump absorbed power [kW]		
Pump	P = pressure side [bar]	$CP[0] = 10^{K_1+K_2 \cdot \log_{10} W_p + K_3 \cdot \log_{10} W_p^2}$ $F_p = 10^{C_1+C_2 \cdot \log_{10} P + C_3 \cdot \log_{10} P^2}$	[11]
		$CP[0] = 10^{K_1+K_2 \cdot \log_{10} Volume + K_3 \cdot \log_{10} Volume^2}$	
Steam separator	Volume [m ³] Diameter [m]	$F_{P_{vessel}} = \frac{(P+1) \cdot D}{2 \cdot (850 - 0.6 \cdot (P+1))} + 0.00315$ 0.0063 $C_{BM} = CP_T[0] \cdot (B_1 + B_2 \cdot F_M \cdot F_{P_{vessel}})$	[11]
Turbine	W_T = Turbine Power [kW]	$CP[0] = 10^{K_1+K_2 \cdot \log_{10} W_T + K_3 \cdot \log_{10} W_T^2}$ $C_{BM} = CP_T[0] \cdot F_{BM_T}$	[11]
Valve (generic)	-	Negligible	-

For each component, LCOE has been evaluated using the following equation [12]:

$$LCOE = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^{30} \frac{plant_{totcost} + variable_{OM}}{(1+r)^j}}{\sum_{j=1}^{30} \frac{W_T \cdot N_h}{(1+r)^j}} \quad (2)$$

$plant_{totcost}$ is the sum of the investment cost of each component in the block increased by 1.5% to account for standard O&M operations. Plant expected operational live time is expected to be 30 years with 7400 h/years of operation.

2.4. LCA Modelling

In addition to the thermodynamic analysis, an environmental cost of the surface plant's construction is also assessed. In particular, we want to express the potential impacts generated in the life cycle of the mechanical components described in the previous chapters. This is achieved by applying the life cycle assessment methodology, which follow the structure defined by ISO14040:2006 and ISO14044:2006. A parametric model was created for both case (ORC and Flash) which, on the basis of the results obtained from the thermodynamic model, could assess the environmental impacts generated by each mechanical component in the plant. In this work, the open-source software OpenLCA was used, which allows to maintain the parametric modeling and to simply evaluate different configurations of the system. The database used is Ecoinvent 3.6 from which datasets were taken for modelling with a cradle-to-gate approach.

2.4.1 Goal and scope

The purpose of this analysis is to calculate the environmental cost of the geothermal surface plant by expressing it as a single score. In order to obtain this value, it is necessary not only to assess the environmental impacts with an LCIA method but also to proceed with the non-mandatory steps of normalization and weighting proposed by the selected method. The model that has been created allows the possibility of using any method of calculating environmental impacts applicable to the database used. The boundaries of the system enclose the surface system and thus the mechanical components that compose the power plant. In view of the environmental exergo analysis the functional unit is each mechanical component analyzed quantified as a number of items.

2.4.2 Life Cycle Inventory

In order to create a parametric model, it was necessary to take several LCIs of existing geothermal plants [5,6,7,8], and alignment and comparison work was carried out for each mechanical component. The aim was to obtain a production process for each component that had the material inputs dependent on the size of the component itself. So once the main materials of each element have been identified, they were associated with the size of the mechanical element.

Notice that also in this case the components of both plant type, even if they have the same functions, has been distinct to underline the different impact due to their specific materials, quantities and construction. On the

basis of these information were obtained some functions to correlate the material quantity with the size of each component. An example is exposed in Figure 4, which represent the characteristic relation concerning the steel of turbine related with the flash model. In this case, a polynomial relation was obtained, but for other materials a linear type relation was applied due to the lack of available data.

Figure 4. Steel correlation for turbine

In the following Table 6 and Table 7 are shown the relationships between the size and the amount of material for each component. The variable “x” represents the size of component while “y” variable is the amount of material. In particular, in flash block: condenser and cooling tower’ size is the heat exchanged, pump’s size is absorbed electric power, steam separator and turbine’s one refers to the generated electric power. These functions are applicable only in the reported range. Notice that GEOENVI guidelines are used for flash condenser and cooling tower due to the limited available data. Regarding ORC block the size of condenser, HRSG and regenerator is heat exchanged and the size of pump and turbine are the same of the flash.

Table 6. Generic Environmental Costs Correlations

Component	Material	Function	Range [kW]
Condenser	Steel	$y = 3,344x$	GEOENVI
	Steel	$y = 0,393x$	
Cooling Tower	Plastic	$y = 2,951$	GEOENVI
	Fibre glass	$y = 1,475$	
Pump	Copper	$y = 3,4754x - 0,0099$	$8 \leq x \leq 1400$
	Steel, chromium steel 18/8	$y = 0,4621x - 0,0013$	
Steam Separator	Steel low alloyed	$y = 0,219x - 1723,6$	$33000 \leq x \leq 272000$
	Stone Wool	$y = 0,172x - 1353,9$	
Turbine	Aluminium wrought alloy	$y = 0,2489x + 199,21$	$20000 \leq x \leq 45000$
	Copper	$y = - 9,9E-6 x^2 + 1,055 x - 14595$	
	Lubricating oil	$y = 0,6667x + 533,58$	
	Steel	$y = - 6,2E-9 x^3 + 2,9E-4 x^2 + 13,89 x - 283665$	
Compressor	Aluminium	$y = 20.884x - 772.81$	$35 \leq x \leq 175$
	Cast iron	$y = 44,561x - 1648,9$	
	Copper	$y = 60,168x - 2308,8$	
Heat exchanger	Steel	$y = 2,0833x + 76,5$	GEOENVI
	Steel	$y = 0,769x$	

Table 7. ORC Environmental Costs Correlations

Component	Material	Function	Range [kW]
Condenser	Steel	$y = 1,574x$	GEOENVI
HRSG	Copper	$y = 0,0682x + 2498,4$	$6400 \leq x \leq 42000$

	Steel	$y = 1,574x$	GEOENVI
Pump	Copper	$y = 0,1564x + 13,988$	$45 \leq x \leq 588$
	Steel	$y = 0,0107x + 312,72$	
Regenerator	Copper	$y = 0,0133x + 568,92$	$1200 \leq x \leq 18000$
	Steel	$y = 1,574x$	GEOENVI
Turbine	Aluminium	$y = 0,5724x - 104,61$	$1000 \leq x \leq 5600$
	Copper	$y = 1,0879x - 627,43$	
	Steel	$y = 31,726x - 24917$	

3. Results

3.1. Metamodel Results

The first metamodel developed has shown interesting trends for both flash stage and ORC blocks. In particular in Figure 5 is shown the predicted power production for a flash power plant at fixed input condition ($T_{in} = 180^{\circ}C$) considering different x_{rel} values for each flash stage block and different number of stages. A maximum value is clearly present in each plot. Moreover, is interesting that for higher number of stages, the optimal value for x_{rel} in the first stage decrease, hence it is convenient for the liquid brine to maintain a higher exergy content so that it can be exploited in the following stages. As for the ORC cycles in figure 6 is shown a comparison between $R1233zd(e)$ and $R1234yf$ in which is clear that the first one is the best choice in all condition except for inlet brine with temperatures below $150^{\circ}C$.

Figure 5. Predicted relative power production for different flash plants with different number of stages.

Figure 6. Predicted power output for $R1233zd(e)$ and $R1234yf$ ORC Cycles

3.2. Comparison with existing plant

In this paragraph the flash stage block previously described is compared with the existing flash plant of Hellisheiði. The Hellisheiði power plant is sited in south-west Iceland, near Reykjavik, which is a high temperature geothermal area. The generation of electricity is realised using two pressure stages with 6 high pressure turbines (45MW) and one low pressure turbine (33 MW) [16]. Operation conditions are shown in Table 8.

Table 8. Hellisheiði operation conditions

Location	Hellisheiði
Geothermal source type	liquid/vapor
Energy generation technology	Double flash
Final energy use	CHP
Installed capacity	Thermal 133 MW _{th} Electric 303,3 MW _{el}
Geothermal flow rate (t/h)	1050
Temperature (°C)	180
Pressure (bar)	10
Specific enthalpy (kJ/kg)	1365
Energy efficiency	Thermal 0,10 Electric 0,23

To compare the flash stage block with an existing plant, the single block is duplicated in series to obtain a double stage block. The input data of the second stage is the separated liquid part of the fluid obtained by the separator in the first stage. The power of each stage and the cost of the whole double flash model has been calculated using the brine conditions of the Hellisheiði site. These results have been compared with the published ones [14] excluding from the total plant cost the values of the components that haven't been considered in the model. The shown data in Table 9 highlight that the model suites properly with the existing plant result.

Table 9. Results comparison

Parameter	Hellisheiði	Metamodels	Error
Power (MW)	303,3	304,8	0.5%
Plant cost (€)	1,352E7	1,352E7	0.002%

3.3. Environmental costs.

To determine the environmental cost of the Hellisheiði power plant with this model, each component had to be duplicated to represent the two different levels of working pressure (high and low pressure). The environmental cost of all mechanical components is evaluated as a single score for each. In this case we use the ILCD midpoint 2011 method and set of normalization and weighting provided by the European Commission EC-JRC Global, equal weighting. The results that have been obtained, shown in Figure 7, reveal that the highest environmental cost is caused first by the turbine and then by the high-pressure condenser. Slightly lower is the cost of the evaporative tower and even lower are the ones of the pumping system and the steam separator. Also, to be underlined is the significant difference between the same types of components at different pressure levels.

Figure 7. Environmental costs of Hellisheiði mechanical components.

This type of environmental analysis is still significantly simplified, since comparing the total sum of the environmental cost of the mechanical components with analyses carried out in the literature overestimates the environmental impacts. Comparing the specific analysis of the mechanical components of Hellisheiði [15] with the model that has been realized in this paper the final impact results to be 17% higher. It should be noted, however, that we are not expressing the potential environmental impact of this system (midpoint level) but an environmental indicator that represents the environmental cost (single score). Therefore, an overestimation is an uncertainty to be considered, but it satisfies the aim of the work.

4. Conclusions

Even though still under development, the code has shown that its capable of correctly model the behaviour of existing power plants and to identify the best configuration for different input condition, at least from a power production perspective. Further development is needed in order to increase the prediction capability of the software and to make possible the correct identification of the best solution on an LCOE or Single score basis.

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